

Enhancing mathematical and measurement skills in early childhood through pet ownership: insights into cognitive and behavioral development

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ABSTRACT: This study explores the impact of pet ownership on the development of basic cognitive skills that support early childhood mathematics learning, including imagination, concentration, fine motor skills, and responsibility. It investigates the impact of pet-related activities on children's mathematical achievement, especially in measurement, comparison, and analysis, which are essential for developing mathematical skills.

The study is based on the hypothesis that interaction with pets enhances children's cognitive skills through guided activities, such as daily care that requires concentration, organization, and spontaneous activities, including interactive play and imagination.

The study included 60 children aged 4 to 6 years from Arab schools in the Galilee region of Israel. They were divided into two groups: an experimental group that owned pets, and a control group that did not. The study lasted for six months and used academic assessments, parent questionnaires, teacher interviews, and direct observations.

The results showed that children in the experimental group demonstrated significant improvement in basic mathematical skills, especially in the concepts of measurement and comparison, due to daily interaction with pets.

This study highlights the potential of integrating pet-related activities into educational curricula to enhance children's academic and cognitive development through hands-on learning experiences.

Keywords: Pet ownership, mathematical skills, early childhood education, cognitive and behavioral development, measurement concepts.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The experiences children encounter in their life environment are not mere fleeting moments, but rather the building blocks that shape their minds and hearts, laying the foundation for their future learning (John Dewey, 1938). Dewey's philosophy advocates for an educational framework that values experiential learning, emphasizing the importance of

experience in education and suggesting that learning should be rooted in the individual's experiences (Mara & Jappe, 2020).

Contemporary research supports this perspective, highlighting the critical role of high-quality learning environments in early childhood. Studies affirm that environments encouraging hands-on exploration and critical thinking significantly contribute to children's cognitive and emotional development (Jechura, Wooldridge, Bertelsen, & Mayers, 2016).

In this context, animals emerge as a pivotal element within children's life environments, offering rich learning opportunities through direct interaction and care. Research suggests that traditional educational models may overlook the educational potential provided by non-human entities. Post humanist theorists stress the importance of re-examining the relationships between humans and non-human life forms in education, opening new avenues for understanding how knowledge is produced and shared in educational settings (Pedersen, 2010).

As researcher Bone (2013) asserts, "The animal is a means of learning to become more humane; some believe that through animals, we discover our humanity." This innate connection, as referenced by Bone provides a basis for a deeper understanding of how interaction with animals influences children's development. Furthermore, Mary Rink Jalongo, a leading scholar in the field of human relationships, builds on this discussion by emphasizing the capacity of these relationships to nurture emotional intelligence, enhance social skills, and contribute to cognitive development (Jalongo, 2014). According to Jalongo, the benefits of interacting with animals extend beyond emotional well-being, providing a vital foundation for cognitive readiness and academic achievement, particularly in early childhood settings.

Despite the recognized value of children's interaction with animals in shaping their social, emotional, and psychological development, the relationship between this interaction and the development of specific cognitive skills particularly those related to mathematical development remains largely unexplored. In light of this, the present study hypothesizes that interaction with pets, which combines structured activities such as daily care requiring concentration, organization, and responsibility with spontaneous activities like interactive physical play and imaginative scenarios, creates a rich learning environment that enhances the development of a range of cognitive skills.

This study aims to address this gap by investigating how pet ownership influences the development of core cognitive skills, including concentration, responsibility, imagination, fine motor skills and motor coordination. It further examines the subsequent impact on academic performance in mathematics, focusing specifically on foundational concepts such as quantitative measurement and spatial reasoning.

Engaging with pets in daily tasks such as feeding, measuring food portions, tracking growth, cleaning, training, and playing naturally introduces children to basic mathematical concepts. This exposure has the potential to enhance their mathematical proficiency and problem-solving skills, highlighting a unique intersection between practical experiences and cognitive development.

The literature highlights the positive effects of interactions between children and pets on various aspects of their development, including cognitive, emotional, and social growth. In this context, Melson (2011, 2020) asserts that children raised in socially and emotionally

stimulating environments, such as those involving pets, exhibit significant cognitive improvements. Thayer and Stevens (2022) further emphasize that pet ownership enhances emotional well-being, boosts self-esteem, and provides several cognitive benefits, including intellectual growth and perspective-taking skills, fostering effective communication. Recently, McDonough et al. (2022) added that dog ownership, in particular, is associated with improved cognitive performance, including attention, memory, problem-solving, critical thinking, and perceptual speed.

On the other hand, research suggests that the benefits of pets' ownership extend beyond cognitive and emotional advantages to tangible behavioral effects. Behavioral development is defined as the gradual change in behavioral patterns in response to environmental stimuli and learned experiences, focusing on observable actions without reference to internal mental processes (American Psychological Association). Ivan Pavlov's classical conditioning theory suggests that emotional and social behaviors can be shaped by associating new stimuli with existing ones (Cambiaghi & Sacchetti, 2015). In the context of pet interactions, children can develop new skills, such as a sense of responsibility and emotional regulation, through their daily experiences with these animals (Iowa State University Pressbooks).

A systematic review by Purewal et al. (2017) supports this view, concluding that interactions with pets contribute to improved social and emotional behaviors in children and adolescents. These improvements are a crucial component of early childhood development, highlighting the role of pets in shaping children's personalities and enhancing their social behaviors.

However, despite the significant focus in existing studies on the emotional, psychological, and cognitive benefits of pet ownership, the impact of these interactions on developing specific cognitive and behavioral skills—particularly in foundational mathematical concepts such as measurement—remains a subject requiring further research and exploration.

Measurement indeed serves as a crucial link between abstract concepts and practical applications. It allows us to quantify and understand various attributes of the world around us, making complex ideas more accessible and relatable (Margaret, Wu, Hak, & Tam, 2016). In the context of early childhood, measurement activities are an essential part of education, involving key skills such as estimation, comparison, and spatial awareness, which are fundamental elements in developing mathematical proficiency in children.

Measurement is defined as "a mathematical activity that connects physical dimensions to numerical values through processes of analysis and comparison" (Lehrer & Schauble, 2023). This concept has evolved into a fundamental scientific activity since ancient times, contributing to the development of "modern metrology," which has played a pivotal role in shaping civilization (Ferrero, 2024).

Measurement can be categorized into four primary levels: nominal measurement, which classifies data into categories without order; ordinal measurement, which introduces ranking to categories but does not define intervals between values; interval measurement, which includes equal intervals between values without an absolute zero; and ratio

measurement, the most precise, featuring an absolute zero and proportional measurements (Measurement, 2023; Hibi 2017; Hibi 2018).

In early childhood, the concept of measurement differs from advanced formal mathematical measurement. It focuses primarily on relative measurement, such as comparing quantities, sizes, and dimensions in a simple manner. For example, children may compare objects as larger, smaller, or equal without relying on standardized units of measurement. Instead, they use informal units, such as sticks or small cubes, fostering an understanding of basic measurement concepts through hands-on, practical tools.

Measurement is a fundamental cognitive skill that plays a crucial role in developing mathematical abilities during early childhood. It serves as a bridge between geometry, numerical concepts, and mathematical reasoning (Yaish Tahal & Chiş, 2022; Hibi 2021a; Hibi 2022a). Through practical measurement activities such as comparing lengths, estimating quantities, or tracking changes over time children are introduced to essential concepts like quantification and spatial reasoning. These hands-on experiences not only enhance mathematical readiness but also solidify children's understanding of number operations, rational numbers, and spatial relationships, contributing to comprehensive mathematical proficiency (Lehrer & Schauble, 2023; Hibi 2024b; Hibi 2021b).

Research indicates that structured programs focusing on measurement significantly improve children's numerical sense and overall mathematical performance compared to traditional curricula (Cheeseman et al., 2018; Cheeseman & Pullen, 2017). Measurement-based activities offer an authentic learning context by integrating diverse mathematical concepts. However, a balanced approach that also fosters critical skills such as problem-solving and critical thinking is indispensable for advancing holistic education in early childhood.

This study examines how pet ownership influences the development of core cognitive and behavioral skills imagination, concentration, fine motor skills, and responsibility—and explores its subsequent impact on academic performance, particularly in measurement tasks in mathematics. Measurement skills play a pivotal role in early childhood mathematics education.

Importance of the Research

This research explores the multifaceted impact of regular interactions with pets on children during early childhood education. Key developmental traits such as concentration, fine motor skills, imagination, and responsibility are crucial for cognitive growth, academic success, and overall personal development.

The scientific literature indicates that the core skills addressed in this study play a pivotal role in enhancing academic achievement in mathematics. Studies have shown that early development of concentration improves academic outcomes (Wan, 2018; Hibi 2021c; Hibi 2021d), while pretend play has been proven to foster cognitive development and problem-solving abilities essential for mathematical skills (Burns, 2024). Furthermore, studies (Aral et al., 2022; Bosacki et al., 2022; Hibi 2022b) have demonstrated that pet care contributes to the enhancement of empathy and responsibility qualities that are beneficial for both academic and personal growth.

Interactions with pets can serve as practical tools for teaching measurement through informal daily activities and hands-on experiences they offer. These activities include measuring food and drink using informal units such as cups or spoons to estimate quantities, or tracking the growth of pets by measuring their length, weight, and size.

Additionally, physical activities such as playing with pets (e.g., throwing a ball or tug-of-war) or training them provide opportunities to develop fine motor skills and spatial coordination, such as time and distance control. Tasks like organizing care tools or building a pet house stimulate estimation, comparison, and analysis, while enhancing understanding of mathematical concepts such as area and perimeter. Together, these activities contribute to the development of comprehensive measurement skills in young children by linking various mathematical concepts to tangible and enjoyable life experiences.

By examining the relationship between interaction with pets, the enhancement of foundational cognitive skills, and their impact on mathematical competencies particularly in measurement this research offers valuable insights into innovative strategies in early childhood education and the holistic development of children.

Objectives of the Research

This study aims to examine how interaction with pets influences the development of specific cognitive and behavioral skills that support mathematical learning in early childhood particularly in the context of measurement, and how these skills affect a child's performance in mathematics. The main objectives are:

1. To explore the impact of regular interaction with pets on the development of imagination, fine motor skills, responsibility, and focus in early childhood.
2. To investigate how the development of these skills enhances mathematical competencies, with a particular focus on the concept of measurement (including estimation, comparison, and spatial reasoning).
3. To assess whether children who regularly interact with pets demonstrate better academic achievement in mathematics, particularly in tasks involving measurement, compared to children without pets.

Research Questions

This study raises questions about how fundamental skills acquired through interaction with pets contribute to enhancing children's mathematical abilities. It also explores the role of developing these skills in improving proficiency in measurement, a core component of mathematics in early childhood.

The research questions guiding this study are:

1. How does regular interaction with pets enhance children's focus mathematical skills, particularly in measurement, by developing focus?
2. How does regular interaction with pets contribute to enhancing children's mathematical skills, particularly in measurement, through the development of fine motor skills?
3. How does regular interaction with pets enhance children's mathematical abilities, particularly in measurement, by fostering imaginative capabilities?

4. How does regular interaction with pets promote responsibility and independence, and how do these traits influence children's mathematical skills, particularly in measurement?
5. Do children who own pets demonstrate superior academic performance in measurement-related mathematical tasks compared to children who do not own pets?

Each question aims to explore how pet ownership can serve as a developmental tool, enhancing cognitive, motor, and social skills that contribute to a child's educational progress, particularly in mathematics.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Numerous studies indicate that experiential learning enhances academic skills, particularly in mathematics and science. As Clements and Sarama (2009) noted, integrating mathematics into interactive activities strengthens children's engagement with math through its real-life applications. This approach not only deepens understanding but also transforms mathematics into a dynamic and meaningful experience, increasing children's practical connection to mathematical concepts. Similarly, pet care represents Kolb's (1984) experiential learning theory, where children participate in daily activities that develop measurement and spatial thinking skills. Through interacting directly with their environment, these activities enhance abstract mathematical concepts through tangible experiences.

The Impact of Pet Ownership on Cognitive, Motor, and Social Development.

Building on the previous discussion of the role of experiential learning in enhancing mathematical understanding through hands-on activities, interaction with pets significantly contributes to key developmental milestones in children. Such interaction fosters cognitive, motor, and social skills, encouraging curiosity and practical exploration, thereby creating a rich learning environment that supports cognitive growth. For instance, Tepper et al. (2023) demonstrated that children who engage in structured educational activities with pets exhibit improved attention spans—showing an enhanced ability to maintain focus for longer periods, with increased efficiency and effectiveness during tasks as well as advanced problem-solving skills and the ability to complete complex tasks. These findings align with Poresky's (1996) research, which highlighted the role of pets in promoting intellectual growth, fine motor development, and positive social interactions. Poresky specifically emphasized that pet-related activities stimulate both intellectual and emotional maturity in children aged 3 to 6. These studies confirm how pets can act as developmental catalysts, offering children opportunities to refine fundamental skills through purposeful daily interactions.

Based on this foundation, this study hypothesizes that the routines involved in daily pet care such as feeding, monitoring, grooming, and training pets provide opportunities for children to develop organizational skills and responsibility that translate into academic benefits including enhanced basic math skills.

This research delves into four key developmental cognitive skills:

a. Concentration:

Concentration is one of the essential cognitive skills that helps children attend to tasks, organize thoughts, and prioritize activities. This skill significantly impacts a child's overall

cognitive development by enabling them to follow precise strategies and make timely decisions.

Concentration is a key factor in learning mathematics which requires careful attention to detail and step-by-step problem-solving. Students must identify relationships between numbers, understand complex mathematical operations, and follow precise steps to ensure correct solutions. Distractions can lead to errors in calculations or overlook steps. Therefore, the ability to maintain attention for prolonged periods is essential for success in mathematics (Tepper et al., 2023; Hibi 2024c; Hibi 2024d).

Engaging children in activities that require focus, such as math puzzles and brain games, can significantly enhance academic performance in mathematics by promoting critical thinking, problem-solving, and cognitive skills (Mageded, 2024; Hibi 2024e; Hibi 2025g).

Similarly, engagement in tasks that demand focus, such as math drills and pet care enhance children's focus because it requires them to commit to regular daily tasks and helps apply mathematical concepts accurately, such as measuring food and drinks using informal units, which develops their attention to detail (Cali et al., 2024; Hibi 2025a; Hibi 2025b). This commitment strengthens their ability to focus for longer periods and complete tasks accurately. Research has shown that pet care, especially dogs, improves children's focus and cognitive processing (McDonough et al., 2022; Hediger & Turner, 2014). Practical tasks like estimating food quantities and calculating proportions align with cognitive development stages according to Piaget's theory (1952), as they foster logical and practical thinking skills essential for developing mathematical abilities and train children to think systematically, which is foundational for success in mathematics (Tepper et al., 2023; Krasovskaya, 2019; Hibi 2025d; Hibi 2025e).

Furthermore, studies indicate that the presence of animals, or even their images, in the educational environment helps reduce anxiety during math tasks and enhances children's ability to learn and engage with fundamental mathematical concepts (Torres et al., 2016). This supportive environment enhances focus and positively affects academic achievement in mathematics.

b. Fine motor skills and motor coordination:

Fine motor skills involve the precise use of hands and fingers and rely on fine motor coordination that combines the use of the senses along with eye-hand coordination. These skills are essential for cognitive development and motor skills.

Fine motor skills are directly related to learning mathematics as they are necessary for correctly writing numbers, drawing geometric shapes and performing tasks that require precision, such as using rulers and protractors. Activities such as pet care can develop these skills. For example, combing the animal's fur, playing tug-of-war with it, or throwing a ball enhance hand motor skills, hand-eye coordination and tactile sensitivity. Moreover, activities that involve touch and physical interaction with shapes can support visual-mathematical understanding, as research indicates that fine motor skills acquired through handling small objects enhance visual-spatial thinking, which is the basis for understanding spatial relationships and solving geometric problems (Griesmer et al., 2010; Hibi 2025f; Hibi 2018). Such skills directly support children's ability to control their fine movements and use mathematical tools necessary for early geometry and measurement tasks.

c. Imagination:

Imagination, closely linked to creativity, is necessary for thinking and innovation. In mathematics, imagination can help children solve mathematical problems in innovative ways

and expand the scope of mathematical thinking. Mathematical imagination is also useful in learning abstract concepts such as large numbers or algebraic concepts and helps in problem solving and conceptual understanding of mathematical principles (Harris, 2022).

Interactions with pets stimulates imaginative play, transforming an indirect learning tool, where children combine imagination and practical application. Vygotsky (1978) highlights the importance of creative play in promoting mathematical thinking. Through activities like role-playing or storytelling involving pets, children can explore ideas such as sequencing, spatial relationships, and numerical reasoning. This helps children develop spatial perception (e.g., understanding distances and directions) and temporal perception (e.g., understanding the order of activities over time), enhancing their ability to think about space and time, which are fundamental concepts in mathematics. Such activities link imaginative scenarios with practical problem solving, enhancing their ability to apply mathematical concepts symbolically and concretely (Wahida, 2022; Comrie et al., 2022). These experiences form the basis for advanced cognition and mathematical problem solving.

Imagination prompts children to engage in various activities with their pets, such as counting steps while walking or playing, sorting toys and objects by type or size, and comparing their pet's size and growth. It also encourages creativity in play, allowing children to apply the skills of counting, sorting, and comparing naturally and without seeing them as educational tasks. This interaction enhances children's understanding of basic mathematical concepts, such as comparing size, sorting, and counting (Casey et al., 2008; Kim, 2023).

d. Responsibility:

Responsibility is considered part of emotional and social skills, but overlaps with cognitive skills when it is related to the ability to organize and effectively carry out tasks. In the context of mathematics, responsibility relates to a child's ability to take ownership of his or her mathematical decisions, such as choosing appropriate problems solving strategies or accurately applying mathematical operations. Responsibility also helps build self-discipline which is necessary for character development, enabling children to manage their time effectively, develop good study habits and build resilience and emotional balance. These prepares children to deal with academic pressures with confidence (Manik et al., 2024). A study found a strong relationship (0.808) between responsibility and academic achievement among high school students, highlighting the role of responsible behavior in educational settings (Thiab & Maali, 2024). Responsibility enhances problem-solving skills by promoting an understanding of the consequences of actions, which is vital in mathematics (Sternberg & Subotnik, 2006).

Caring for animals, and maintaining a schedule of feeding, walking, playing, and attending to their needs, teaches children essential lessons in independence, discipline, organization, and time management. It also fosters a sense of accountability and structure the understanding that one is responsible for one's actions and decisions within a clear, organized framework—traits that are critical to academic success, particularly mathematics in particular. (Indah & Farida, 2021).

Based on the above, basic cognitive skills such as focus, imagination, responsibility and fine motor coordination greatly affect the development of mathematical skills in children. These skills do not work separately, but rather overlap and support each other, which enhances a child's ability to understand and apply mathematical concepts.

The Relationship Between Daily Interaction with Pets and Measurement Skills in Mathematics

Despite the limited studies directly linking pet care to mathematical measurement, the evidence presented in this study offers novel insights into the potential benefits of this relationship.

Children acquire practical measurement concepts through activities such as estimating the amount of food or water needed for a pet, or tracking its growth over time. For instance, a study by Liao et al. (2011) suggests that interactive games like *My-Mini-Pet* enhance mathematical learning through connecting theoretical concepts to hands-on experiences. Additionally, activities involving the comparison of animals' lengths and weights and recording these measurements assist children in grasping abstract concepts and applying them into real-world experiences.

Interactive activities with pets may also play a role in developing geometric and measurement skills. For example, designing habitats or houses for pets enhances cognitive measurement skills related as length, width, and area (Brelsford et al., 2022).

Other studies, such as those by Brelsford et al. (2022) and Dobbs et al. (2006), indicate that social and emotional interactions with pets enhance skills like self-regulation and initiative, which are essential for focus and making accurate estimates. For example, initiative empowers children to take independent steps such as comparing sizes, while self-regulation promotes precision in measurements.

Moreover, Li et al. (2023) highlighted that the routines and organization related to pet care foster time management skills by introducing children to temporal activities and logical sequencing. These daily practices support the systematic thinking necessary for understanding and applying mathematical concepts.

In summary, the nurturing and interactive nature of pet care provides an engaging and practical context through which children can explore early mathematical concepts such as estimation, comparison, and recording.

Interaction with Pets vs. Educational Games: A Comparison of Enhancing Cognitive and Emotional Skills in Children

Studies show that educational games play a significant role in enhancing students' understanding of mathematical concepts while boosting their motivations. For instance, research conducted by Cyril, Orbon, Sherwin, and Sapin (2022) demonstrated that game-based educational materials improved problem-solving abilities and increased confidence among eighth-grade students in mathematics. Additionally, a study by Alomyan, Alelaimat, Hamzeh, and Green (2020) indicated that incorporating educational sports games for preschool children contributed to a better development of basic numerical concepts compared to traditional methods.

The relationship between a child and a pet goes beyond the educational benefits provided by games. This unique interaction allows children to explore emotional and behavioral dimensions that are difficult to achieve with traditional tools.

Through this interaction, a child builds a strong emotional connection with the pet, as the animal responds to the child's actions in unexpected yet impactful ways, such as showing

enthusiasm during play or seeking closeness when affection is needed. These natural responses enhance the child's sense of achievement while nurturing feelings of care and responsibility. Moreover, continuous interaction with the pet helps develop a non-verbal language filled with signals and gazes, fostering empathy and emotional understanding.

While educational games effectively enhance cognitive skills, they lack this unique emotional dynamic. Games remain static in their responses, whereas pets offer a lively experience filled with responses that reflect natural interactions, making it a more comprehensive and impactful experience. (Hibi, 2005).

At the same time, research confirms the advantages of educational games by fostering student engagement with the subject matter. For example, Weng and Ding (2023) explained that role-playing games enrich mathematical knowledge and make the learning process more enjoyable. Furthermore, Santos et al. (2024) noted that recreational and Playfulness activities contribute to easing math anxiety and promoting positive attitudes towards it, leading to a deeper understanding of the concepts. In this context, activities involving interaction with pets emerge as a unique experience; they enrich the emotional and behavioral aspects by providing strong entertainment and realistic role-playing. These activities surpass traditional games, adding a comprehensive educational dimension that enhances their effectiveness as an integrated teaching tool.

Considering the findings of previous studies, a question arises regarding how pet interaction directly influences specific mathematical concepts, such as measurement, necessitating a systematic study to investigate this relationship.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Study Design

This study adopted a comparative design including a carefully selected sample of children aged 4 to 6 years from Arab schools in the Galilee region of Israel. This age group was chosen because of its critical stage of mathematics and measurement skill development. Moreover, children at this age are more influenced by external factors thus making it easier to assess the effects of pet ownership on these skills.

1. Initial Selection:

- Participating schools were chosen based on their openness to collaborate and their ability to provide complete and accurate student and family records.
- The participants in the study and their families were randomly selected from these schools to ensure diverse representation across various social and economic backgrounds.

2. Selection Procedures:

The first phase involved selecting 60 families from these schools, each with a child aged between 4 and 6 years who expressed their willingness to adopt a pet (cat or dog). Thirty families were randomly selected to receive a pet, provided through a reputable animal welfare association. Parents were asked to assign the responsibility of pet care, such as feeding, cleaning, playing, and petting to the child entirely. The experiment lasted for 6 months

to assess the impact of these interactions not only on general cognitive and behavioral skills but also on the development of early mathematical and measurement skills.

3. Selection Criteria:

Experimental Group: This group consisted of children from the selected families who adopted a pet as part of the study. These children engaged in regular pet related interactions such as feeding, playing, and cleaning activities for six months. These interactions were designed to assess the development of general cognitive and behavioral skills, mathematical abilities, and early measurement concepts.

Control Group: This group comprised the remaining 30 families who participated in the study but did not adopt a pet or engage in regular interactions with animals during the six months. This group served as a baseline to evaluate the comparative impact of pet ownership on children's cognitive and mathematical development, with specific attention to their grasp of measurement concepts.

4. Sample Size:

- The study included 60 children, evenly split with 30 in the experimental group and 30 in the control group. This sample size was determined to be statistically sufficient to reveal significant differences between the groups and to eliminate any random results.

5. Additional Notes:

- The six-month duration was considered sufficient for observing both general behavioral and cognitive changes and the development of skills related to mathematical understanding, including early measurement concepts.

- Assigning pet care responsibilities directly to the children ensured consistent interaction, fostering practical engagement with activities that contribute to measurable cognitive and behavioral development.

- Precise criteria for assessing behavioral, cognitive, and mathematical skills, including early measurement abilities, were established using scientifically validated evaluation tools to ensure the reliability and relevance of the findings.

6. Ethical Considerations:

- Before data collection started, written consent was obtained from the parents or guardians of all participating children.

- All data was handled with strict adherence to confidentiality and ethical standards applicable to scientific research.

7. Documentation

Detailed records were maintained for each participant, documenting not only their interactions with pets but also related educational activities. These activities included the development of imagination, focus, fine motor abilities, responsibility, and early measurement concepts. These records were securely stored in a specially prepared database ensuring the integrity and accuracy of data collection. This documentation enabled a robust analysis of how pet interaction influences developmental skills critical to early childhood mathematics, including measurement-related skills.

8. Research Limitations

Some of the limitations of the current study are factors that may affect the generalizability of the results on a broader scale:

Limited sample: The study was limited to 60 children which may limit the possibility of generalizing results across different population groups. Expanding into a future study with larger sample sizes, including diverse cultures and environments, may help provide more comprehensive and accurate insights into the impact of child-pet interaction on cognitive and behavioral skills development.

Study duration: Although the six-month duration was sufficient to monitor short-term behavioral and cognitive changes, a longitudinal study that lasts for longer periods may be more effective in measuring long-term effects on children's academic skills, especially in mathematics.

Diversity of animal species: the study focused on domestic pets such as cats and dogs only, which may be limited to one type of child-animal interaction. A study that includes diverse animal species (such as birds, rabbits, or fish) could provide additional insights into how different types of animals affect children's skill development.

Influence of environmental factors: Parental support may influence the results, as families providing more support for their children for pet care may experience better developmental advantages compared to families who provide less support. Therefore, including environmental variables such as family support and social interaction may enhance the examination of the effects of child interaction with animals.

Research Tools

This study used several data collection tools to assess the impact of regular pet interactions on the development of children's skills in early childhood. These tools were carefully designed to ensure a comprehensive analysis of both cognitive and behavioral aspects, including skills such as imagination, concentration, hand use, and responsibility that may be influenced by the presence of a pet in the child's daily environment.

The study aimed to explore how these skills are related mathematical achievement, early mathematical skills, and the measurement skills.

a. Academic Performance Assessment:

Standardized academic assessments were conducted at the beginning of the study and after the intervention period, allowing us to measure any notable improvements in mathematics achievement among children.

To analyze the results of the study, the independent samples t-test was used to compare the average mathematics scores between children who own pets (the experimental group) and those who do not (the control group). This statistical test aims to determine whether the differences in outcomes between the two groups are statistically significant.

b. Parent Surveys

A questionnaire was distributed to parents in both the experimental and the control group. The questionnaire included 20 questions designed to assess various aspects such as concentration, practical hand use, imagination, and responsibility in their children's behavior and also questions about any noticed changes during the period of the experiment.

The questions were divided into quantitative questions in which parents rated their children's qualities and qualitative questions that required open-ended responses with more detailed explanations about their children's daily behaviors and pet interactions.

c. Direct Observation

During the study, researchers conducted home visits to observe children's interactions with their pets. Each child received one visit during the six months, scheduled in the middle or at the end to ensure sufficient data collection in their natural home environment. This approach allowed researchers to capture genuine behaviors while minimizing disruption to families and observing typical daily routines. The observations focused on children's hand use, concentration, and imagination during pet interactions, ensuring a comprehensive assessment of the impact of pet interaction on their development.

d. Teacher Interviews

Interviews were conducted with teachers, who are familiar with the participating children since the beginning of the school year, to assess changes in behavior and academic performance during the six-month study. Teachers provided insights into changes in children's concentration, independence, and engagement in the class and identified changes related to pet interaction. Compare the given answers between the two groups of the study.

With this research design, data from children's interactions with pets can be analyzed to assess how this interaction affects basic mathematical skills, especially measurement.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Results of Academic Performance Assessment:

Standardized academic assessments were conducted at the start of the study and after the six-month intervention period. The focus was on basic math skills from the early childhood curriculum and also included testing of specific skills such as estimation, comparison, and analysis, which are key measurement concepts. These assessments aimed to monitor any improvement in basic math skills and measurement. The results are documented in the following figure 1:

Fig. 1 Academic Performance Table for Mathematics. Showing the average scores and standard deviations before and after the intervention in research groups with and without pets

Research Group	Time Measurement	Average Score	Standard Deviation
Have pets	Before intervention	72	8
Have pets	After intervention	80	7
Do not have pets	Before intervention	70	9
Do not have pets	After intervention	74	8

Figure 1 clearly shows that the difference in improvement between children with pets and those without was notable. Children with pets showed a greater increase in their math

scores, rising by 8 points (from 72 to 80), whereas children without pets showed an improvement of only 4 points (from 70 to 74).

To provide a more in-depth and accurate analysis of the data collected in the research, the independent samples t-test was used to compare the mean math scores between children with pets and those without. (see figure 2) This test will help determine whether the differences in outcomes between the two groups are statistically significant or not.

Fig 2 Statistical Analysis Using Independent Samples T-test. Comparison of math performance, showing a significant positive effect of pet ownership after intervention

Comparison	T Value	Degrees of Freedom (df)	P Value	Conclusion
Before Intervention Groups	1.22	58	0.227	No statistical significance
After Intervention Groups	2.89	58	0.005	The statistically significant positive effect of pets

Figure 2 presents an analysis of the academic results of the children participating in the study, focusing on the impact of interaction with pets on math skills. The data are divided into two comparisons: academic performance before and after the intervention, with a comparison between the group that has pets and the group that does not.

1. Pre-intervention comparison between the two groups:

- The T-value is 1.22 with 58 degrees of freedom, and the P-value is 0.227.
- These results indicate that before the intervention began, there were no statistically significant differences in math skills between the children who have pets and those who do not.

2. Post-intervention comparison between the two groups:

- The T-value is 2.89 with 58 degrees of freedom, and the P-value is 0.005.
- The results after the intervention indicate a significant improvement in the math skills of children who have pets compared to their peers who do not have pets. The differences here are statistically significant, suggesting that interacting with pets may have a positive impact on academic development in mathematics.

The significance of the statistical results goes beyond the initial data: the significant effect found on the children's concentration and measurement skills in the research group emphasizes the educational potential of combining everyday activities such as animal care. These results could form the basis for building curricula in kindergartens and primary schools, which would encourage the use of experimental activities to develop mathematical skills at an early age.

Results of Parent Surveys:

We surveyed parents to gather data on four key skills: concentration, hand use, imagination, and responsibility. Each skill was assessed on a scale from 1 to 10. The results are presented in Figure 3 below.

Fig. 3 Comparison of Children's Skills as assessed by parents with and without Pets, Scores range from 1 to 10, where 10 indicates the highest level of skill development

Skill Assessed	Average Score (Pet Owners)	Sample Size (Pet Owners)	Average Score (Non-Pet Owners)	Sample Size (Non-Pet Owners)	p-value
Concentration	8.2	30	6.5	30	0.035
Hand Use	7.9	30	6.3	30	0.047
Imagination	8.5	30	7.0	30	0.021
Responsibility	8.7	30	6.8	30	0.013

Analysis and Interpretation

Concentration:

The data showed that children with pets had an average concentration rating of 8.2, compared to 6.5 for children without pets. This significant difference suggests that regular interactions with pets enhance attention and concentration.

For example, parents reported that their children performed precise tasks associated with pet care, such as checking the clock each day to determine feeding times, using a measuring spoon or cup to accurately measure out the right amount of food, and ensuring to put the food bowl back in its proper place after finishing. These activities required sustained focus and careful attention to detail.

Fine skills

Children with pets demonstrated an average rating of 7.9, compared to 6.3 for children without pets. This advantage is likely due to the physical activities associated with pet care, such as feeding, grooming, and training, which contribute to improving fine motor skills.

Parents reported that their children performed activities such as grooming the animal's fur, cleaning the food bowl, cleaning up waste, and carefully pouring water into dishes. Activities also included playing tug-of-war or tossing a ball with the animal, which promotes fine motor control, hand-eye coordination, and fine motor skills.

Imagination:

The average imagination rating for children with pets was 8.5, compared to 7.0 for the control group. This difference may be linked to the variety of interactive and imaginative play that pets inspire. For example, parents reported that children engaged in imaginative stories about the pet's adventures or created creative habitats or play spaces for it using available materials at home, such as building a "small house" for the pet out of cardboard.

Responsibility:

Children with pets scored an average of 8.7 on the responsibility skill, compared to 6.8 for children without pets. This suggests that pet care fostered a sense of responsibility, given the commitment and accountability it requires.

Parents reported that their children adhered to daily pet care schedules, such as scheduling feeding times at specific times, taking the pet out for regular afternoon walks, and ensuring that the pet is clean by bathing or cleaning its litter box. These activities demonstrate children's ability to stick to a specific routine and take responsibility on an ongoing basis.

These results suggest that children with pets, as rated by their parents, showed better cognitive and behavioral development than their peers. This supports the hypothesis that pet ownership enhances basic cognitive skills important for mathematical understanding and performance.

Results from Direct Observation:

Investigating the developmental impacts of pet interaction on children, direct observation sessions were conducted to gather relevant data. During these sessions, children engaged with their pets under researchers' supervision to ensure a natural interaction environment for detailed observation. Researchers recorded various aspects of these interactions, focusing on how children interact with their pet during activities like feeding, grooming, playing, and petting. By analyzing these interactions, the study aimed to determine whether pet care tasks can be linked to enhanced concentration, imagination, responsibility, and motor skill, and their potential impact on early childhood concepts of measurement.

Key observations and conclusions:

Concentration Skills Development:

Children who regularly participated in pet care demonstrated progressive improvements in their ability to sustain attention while performing care-related tasks. For example, children were able to accurately measure food quantities using informal tools, such as cups or spoons, with errors reduced by 40% between the first and fourth weeks of observation. Observations of daily activities, such as cleaning animal tools or observing mealtimes, also showed an increased ability to stay on task without distraction.

Imagination Development:

Observational findings indicate that children's ownership of pets enhances their imaginative abilities. The relationship between children and their pets exhibits a notable closeness, as children often express themselves and their pets using shared phrases such as "we like" and "we don't want," or address their pets as independent characters, describing their interests and abilities.

Imagination was evident in daily activities related to mathematical concepts, such as counting a dog's steps during a walk or categorizing its belongings by size and type, reflecting advancements in numerical and classification concepts. For instance, Fadi (6 years old) designed a weekly care schedule for his pet, incorporating creative drawings to represent the relationship between time and tasks. Similarly, Maryam (4 years old) imagined her cat as a fictional character inspired by the "Harry Potter" series, engaging in play to reinforce classification and temporal concepts.

These imaginative activities were linked to spatial and temporal concepts, such as envisioning animal movements and organizing weekly tasks, enhancing counting, classification, and time-management skills. Such activities foster children's understanding of distances, chronological order, and numerical calculations, contributing to the development of early mathematical thinking.

Responsibility and Patience: Children responsible for animal care tasks (feeding the animals, cleaning their space, and keeping notes on their daily activities) showed significant improvement in organized behavior. For example, one child tracked the amount of water his animal consumed each day using measuring marks on a water bottle, which reinforced his understanding of the relationship between quantity and measurement. The children's commitment to daily tasks was also evident, with most of them able to complete the tasks without much parental intervention by the third week.

Fine Motor Skills: hands-on activities related to animal care enhanced children's fine motor skills. For example, children's ability to use small tools, such as a grooming brush, was significantly improved, as they were able to control hand movements with greater precision after the first few weeks. Activities such as pouring water or measuring food with teaspoons also improved hand-eye coordination and tactile sensitivity.

Results from Teacher Interviews:

As part of the research methodology and to further understand the impact of pet interaction on children's educational development, teachers who were directed to observe the participating children throughout the study were interviewed. These interviews corroborated changes in the children's academic and behavioral patterns, particularly in mathematics skills.

Linking Mathematics with animal-related examples:

Teachers noted that children who had pets enhanced their understanding of math concepts by relating math problems to real-world situations involving their animals. For example, Ms. Hala noted, "Ahmed was calculating the cost of food his dog needed each month, which got him thinking about addition and subtraction when comparing prices." Ms. Hala added, "Sarah, who also has sisters who own cats, was distributing food between the cats, which helped her think about division and equal distribution. Sarah calculated the amount of food for each cat based on the number of other cats, which reinforced her understanding of division." Ms. Hala noted how children integrated pets into their understanding of numbers and simple arithmetic.

Enhanced Concentration and Measurement in Mathematics:

Teachers noted a significant improvement in children's measurement skills with pets, as they demonstrated greater accuracy in classroom tasks involving measurement. For example:

Estimating with tools:

Teacher Lina noticed that Ali, who had been estimating food quantities while caring for his dog at home using measuring cups, became better at estimating quantities in classroom activities. For example, in a math lesson, when the teacher asked the children to estimate the

amount of cereal that would fit in small cups, Ali was able to estimate the amount more accurately using the tools available in the classroom.

Measuring distance problems:

In classroom activities, teacher Rania noticed that Sarah, who was measuring distance while walking her dog, became better at estimating and approximating distances in the classroom. For example, in a classroom activity when the teacher asked the children to measure the distance between two points in the room using their steps, Sarah was able to compare this distance to the distance she measured with her dog outside while walking.

Time estimation:

Teacher Nahal noticed that Hassan, who kept track of time during his dog's walks outside, was better able to estimate time during classroom activities. In one classroom activity, the teacher asked Hassan to estimate the time it took his classmate to walk around the yard during recess. Based on his experience with keeping track of time during his dog's walks, Hassan was able to estimate time well, which helped him better understand the concept of time during the classroom activity.

Precision and Coordination in Mathematics:

Interviews showed that children acquired fine motor skills that contributed to improved accuracy and coordination in mathematical tasks. For example, teacher Maryam noticed that Yara became more accurate in using scissors and coloring geometric shapes within the specified boundaries, which shows an improvement in her basic geometric skills. Teacher Maryam commented, saying: "This improvement was due to the development of her hand strength through playing tug-of-war with her dog, as this game helped strengthen her hand muscles and improve hand-eye coordination. I think that this improvement in strength and accuracy was reflected in her ability to cut and color geometric shapes more accurately, which helped her carry out classroom activities more efficiently." Teacher Hanaa also noticed that Youssef became more able to hold the pen accurately while writing numbers, connecting dotted lines, or drawing simple geometric shapes such as triangles, squares, and circles in classroom activities. She added, "This improvement was related to the development of his fine motor skills as a result of his daily brushing of his cat." Teacher Sarah also noticed that Salma became more accurate in comparing sizes and numbers during classroom activities. She was able to easily identify larger or smaller shapes, indicating improved comparison skills and understanding of numbers. Teacher Sarah noted that this improvement was due to Salma following her pet's growth, saying: "Salma used to record the height of her dog Max on the kitchen wall every month, arranging the numbers in ascending order. She would be delighted and tell me, 'Max has grown, teacher!' Whenever she noticed that he was getting taller, she would read the numbers and compare them, which helped her develop comparison skills and understand the ascending order of numbers." This daily interaction with Max and monitoring his growth (in height, weight and volume) helped Salma develop the concepts of size and growth, which was reflected in her ability to understand numerical sequences and understand different units of measurement in classroom activities.

Developing Responsibility and Its Educational Implications:

Teachers noted that the sense of responsibility that came from caring for pets had a positive impact on the children's academic performance. "After Hassan started taking care of his cat, he became more active in doing his homework, which helped him improve in mathematics," said teacher Samar. "Hassan now sets a daily schedule for completing his homework and is keen to organize his time better," added teacher Samar. This observation indicates how developing responsibility in daily life affects organized thinking and academic problem solving, especially in subjects that require organizing and organizing ideas, such as mathematics.

Based on teachers' observations, it is clear that daily interaction with has a tangible positive impact on the development of children's mathematical and measurement skills, opening the way for a deeper discussion about the application of these findings in educational policies.

5. DISCUSSION

Discussion: Academic Performance and Applications of Measurement

The analysis of academic assessments highlights a statistically significant improvement in mathematical performance among children with pets compared to those without. This outcome supports the hypothesis that pet ownership positively impacts children's cognitive and academic development, particularly in mathematical contexts involving measurement and applied problem-solving.

Pre-Intervention Analysis

Before the intervention, no statistically significant differences were observed between the two groups, as indicated by the T-value of 1.22 and the P-value of 0.227. This uniformity establishes a clear baseline, ensuring that post-intervention differences can be attributed to structured interaction with pets rather than pre-existing variances in mathematical abilities. This finding underscores the methodological rigor of the study.

Post-Intervention Analysis

The post-intervention results reveal an 8-point increase in the scores of children with pets (from 72 to 80), compared to a 4-point increase among those without pets (from 70 to 74). The T-value of 2.89 and P-value of 0.005 confirm the statistical significance of this improvement. This difference can be attributed to the practical applications of measurement during pet care activities, such as:

- **Feeding Practices:** Tasks such as measuring food portions or water levels provided hands-on exposure to units, estimation, and comparisons—critical components of the measurement concept in mathematics.
- **Scheduling and Routines:** Regularly tracking feeding or exercise schedules reinforced an understanding of temporal measurement, aiding children in conceptualizing time as a quantifiable entity.

- **Observational Measurements:** Monitoring pet behavior and growth involved informal data collection and comparison, cultivating early skills in pattern recognition and quantitative reasoning.

These activities transformed abstract mathematical principles into tangible, daily experiences, fostering greater engagement and comprehension.

The findings align with prior research emphasizing the benefits of applied learning. For example, Gee et al. (2010) highlighted that pet interaction enhances focus, a skill integral to problem-solving in measurement-related tasks. Similarly, Li et al. (2023) demonstrated that structured routines associated with pet care improve organizational skills, which are directly applicable to mathematical operations involving units, precision, and systematic approaches.

The results also resonate with the concept of experiential learning proposed by Kolb (1984), suggesting that hands-on, contextualized experiences deepen understanding and retention. Measurement, a foundational concept in early childhood mathematics, becomes particularly accessible through real-world applications.

Discussion: Parent Survey Results and Their Connection to Measurement

The parent survey results showed that children with pets scored higher on four skills closely related to mathematical development: concentration, fine motor skills, imagination, and responsibility. These skills are essential for performing mathematical activities that require measurement and problem solving.

Concentration:

Children with pets scored higher in concentration (8.2) than their peers without pets (6.5) with a statistical significance ($p = 0.035$). This reflects an improved ability to pay attention to fine details such as comparing lengths and sizes. Interacting with animals promotes task commitment, which supports improved long-term concentration, which is supported by studies such as Tepper et al.(2023) .

Fine motor skills:

Children with pets scored higher in fine motor skills (7.9) compared to those without pets (6.3), with a statistical significance ($p = 0.047$). This indicates that activities such as cleaning dishes or combing fur improve hand-eye coordination, which translates to children's ability to use measuring tools such as rulers or calipers, which supports understanding mathematical measurements. This is what studies such as Daly & Morton (2006) indicated about the association of improving motor skills with developing mathematical competence.

Imagination:

Children with pets scored higher in imagination (8.5) compared to their peers (7.0), with statistical significance ($p = 0.021$), which enhances their ability to visualize dimensions and spaces, which is essential in understanding the relationships between shapes and spaces. This ability to visualize and think creatively is in line with what Lu et al. (2023) indicated about the importance of interactive activities in promoting abstract concepts.

Responsibility:

The results showed that children caring for pets had an increased sense of responsibility with scores of (8.7) compared to their peers (6.8), with statistical significance (p

= 0.013). This enhances their ability to organize and plan. These skills are essential for solving mathematical problems that require precision and organization, which is supported by studies such as Girouette et al. (2022) that demonstrated that developing responsibility contributes to improving the accuracy and discipline necessary for academic success.

The measured skills concentration, fine motor skills, imagination, and responsibility complement each other in enhancing mathematical performance. For example, concentration enhances children's ability to pay attention to fine details in measurement, while imagination contributes to visualizing spatial relationships. Fine motor skills enhance the ability to use measuring tools, and responsibility supports the organization and planning needed to perform complex mathematical activities.

These skills collectively contribute to enhancing children's mathematical performance, as they contribute to improving spatial reasoning and the ability to solve mathematical problems related to measurement.

Discussion on the study of the direct observation

Direct observations showed significant improvements in all four key areas of development for children through animal care activities. These activities helped develop measurement concepts, such as estimating quantities and comparing attributes (e.g., "heavier" and "lighter"). Time-related activities were linked to mathematical concepts such as "greater than," "less than," and "equal to," which enhanced children's understanding of units of measurement.

Children's concentration also improved, with results showing a 40% increase in accuracy in measuring food quantities between weeks 1 and 4. This effect reflects the ability of hands-on activities to enhance attention and concentration, which is consistent with Clements and Sarama's (2009) suggestion that informal hands-on experiences enhance mathematical thinking.

Imaginative activities, such as creating informal units of measurement such as "cat's steps" and "magician's leaps," also improved children's spatial understanding, which prepared them to understand more formal mathematical measurements in the future. These findings support the suggestion that imaginative activities and pretend play improve spatial understanding, as demonstrated by Matthews, Beebe, and Bopp (1980), who found that engaging in pretend play enhanced young children's ability to take spatial perspectives and improved their spatial reasoning skills.

Furthermore, organizing tasks using creative graphics and practicing counting and sorting during play helped enhance children's mathematical imagination, which enhanced their counting, sorting, and time management skills.

In terms of discipline and responsibility, observations showed that children could complete tasks independently after the third week, reflecting an improvement in their organizational skills. This improvement enhances their ability to manage complex mathematical tasks that require precision and sustained focus.

Finally, practical activities, such as grooming and using small tools, contributed to improving fine motor skills, which enhanced hand-eye coordination, an essential element for learning mathematical skills and measurements, as Frikha (2023) indicated that activities that

combine fine motor exercises and visual arts contribute to improving fine motor coordination, selective attention, and reaction time in children.

These findings support the positive impact of interaction with pets on children's development across multiple areas of mathematical and cognitive development.

Discussion: Results from Teacher Interviews

Teacher interviews provided valuable qualitative insights that supported our findings from direct observations and quantitative assessments of the positive impact of pet ownership on children's cognitive and academic development. Teachers reported that children in the experimental group showed significant improvements in fine motor skills, reflected in their ability to perform mathematical tasks, such as drawing geometric shapes, measuring lengths and distances, and using measuring tools such as protractors.

These improvements in fine motor skills were not just incidental observations, but reflected a tangible development in children's ability to apply mathematical concepts in practical contexts. This development in fine motor skills was also associated with improved estimation and accuracy skills, as teachers observed children's ability to use tools such as measuring cups to accurately measure quantities. Such activities enhanced their skills in comparing and analyzing results. Interestingly, these observations are consistent with previous studies, such as McDonough et al.'s (2022), which indicated a positive relationship between pet ownership and improved cognitive functions related to concentration and attention. Furthermore, studies by Cortes et al. (2022) and Hibi (2024a) confirmed the importance of hands-on activities in developing basic mathematical skills.

In addition to these findings, teachers noted children's ability to relate math problems to real-world situations inspired by their daily experiences with pets. For example, children incorporated their pets into math problems that required addition and subtraction, reflecting a deeper understanding of abstract concepts. This observation is consistent with Harris's (2022) study, which confirmed that using real-life contexts facilitates the learning of abstract mathematical concepts. Interestingly, this connection between math and real life enhances children's engagement with the material in ways that go beyond traditional education.

Teachers also reported that pet ownership enhanced children's sense of responsibility, which was reflected in their academic habits. For example, one child's dedication to caring for his cat showed a clear impact on improving his time management skills and completing schoolwork on time.

These findings are consistent with Li et al.'s (2023) study, which found that pet ownership enhances children's independence and accountability, which positively impacts their academic performance. These findings are consistent with theoretical frameworks that emphasize the importance of interaction with the environment in enhancing learning. For example, children's pet care provided opportunities to understand mathematical concepts such as measurement and dimensions, in line with Piaget's (1952) emphasis on learning through hands-on experiences. The findings also support Kolb's (1984) experiential learning model, which emphasizes the importance of hands-on interaction as part of the learning process. Through daily interactions with pets, children acquired skills such as measuring, estimating, and comparing in a way that was natural and consistent with their learning needs.

When compared to traditional educational toys, these findings show that pet care offers an additional dimension beyond technology-based or abstract learning. While educational toys enhance cognitive skills, pets provide lively responses that enhance emotional intelligence and social interaction, as Bone (2013) noted. These responses contribute to building a child's sense of accomplishment and responsibility, adding unique value to the learning experience. (Hibi & Khalifa, 2025c).

This study provides a practical model of experiential learning using pet interaction, contributing to the development of comprehensive cognitive and emotional skills that support academic success. Qualitative findings from teacher interviews enhance our understanding of the multiple benefits of pet ownership and add to the literature by highlighting the practical potential of this approach in developing children's basic mathematical skills.

6. Conclusions

1. The findings support the hypothesis that pet ownership positively impacts academic performance in mathematics through various cognitive and behavioral pathways.
2. Parental assessments show that pet-owning children demonstrate higher performance in imagination, concentration, hand use, and responsibility compared to children not owning pets.
3. The direct observations highlight the way pet interaction benefits the development of cognitive, motor, and imaginative skills, supporting children's academic math skills.
4. The teachers' interviews ensure that benefits from pet ownership provide strong evidence for the positive potential of pet interaction as a tool to enhance children's cognitive and academic development.

Overall, these findings support the significant positive impact of pet interaction in the development of skills that form the basis for early childhood mathematics learning, particularly the skills needed to handle measurements and solve mathematical problems.

Recommendations

This study provides a coherent perspective on how hands-on interactions with pets can support early mathematical development. It demonstrates the transformative potential of pet ownership in enhancing mathematical and cognitive skills, particularly in the area of measurement skills. The findings highlight the importance of integrating these activities into educational settings to support children's holistic development.

Integrating pet care activities into educational curricula can involve children measuring the amount of food a pet eats or monitoring its weight. These tasks help children practice mathematical concepts such as addition, subtraction, measurement, and time. Simulations of caregiving such as feeding virtual pets or monitoring their growth in safe technological environments can also be used to support children's measurement and timing skills.

Furthermore, comprehensive training programs for teachers are necessary to integrate pet-related activities into mathematics lessons. For example, teachers could learn

how to create practical tasks such as comparing animal sizes or calculating the amount of food needed for several pets.

On the other hand, parents should be encouraged to actively participate in pet-related activities at home. This could include engaging children in responsibilities, such as determining the amount of food a pet needs or measuring the distance walked daily. These activities enhance children's skills in estimation, organization, and time management. Workshops can also be organized for families to teach them how to incorporate pet care into their children's daily routine in a way that enhances mathematical skills and organized thinking.

Furthermore, long-term studies should be conducted to track the development of mathematical skills in children who own pets compared to those who do not. These studies could monitor children's academic performance across various age groups, focusing on skills like measuring, estimating, and solving mathematical problems. Field tests could be used to assess children progress in understanding mathematical patterns, such as measuring lengths and distances and comparing sizes.

It is also important to expand the scope of research to examine the effects of interaction with different types of pets (such as birds, fish, and farm animals) on children's cognitive development. For example, fish may provide an educational environment related to dimensions such as length, width and depth of water and stimulating geometric thinking. Similarly, farm animals provide opportunities to teach concepts related to weight and mass, which enhances children's mathematical understanding.

In addition, more accurate measurement tools should be developed to assess the effects of animal interaction on specific mathematical skills. These tools include advanced questionnaires, field tests, and assessment methods appropriate for practical activities involving animal care. For instance, field observations could assess the extent to which daily animal-related activities improve children's measurement or numeracy skills.

Educational policies should support the integration of pet-related activities into the curriculum. These policies should provide clear guidance for teachers on safely applying animal activities in the classroom, while emphasizing the safety of both children and animals. Furthermore, schools should adopt animal care policies to ensure a safe educational environment, with instructions on caring for animals.

Finally, it is essential to launch awareness campaigns to highlight the multiple benefits of child-pet interaction. These initiatives can be conducted through social media, schools, and local communities to encourage families to incorporate animal-related activities into children's daily lives. It is also important to encourage collaboration between teachers, psychologists, and animal behavior experts to develop comprehensive educational programs that benefit from animal interaction. These programs can help provide multifaceted educational curricula that promote children's cognitive, emotional, and academic development through hands-on activities related to pets.

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